

Efficacy of *Saptasaram Ghan Vati* in the Management of *Kashtartava* (Primary Dysmenorrhea): A Case Study

Dr Nidhi Sharma¹, Dr Asokan V.²

¹P.G SCHOLAR, Dept of *Prasuti Tantra Evum Stri Roga*, Parul Institute of Ayurveda, Parul University, Vadodara

²Ph. D. GAU, Professor, Department of PG Studies in *Prasuti Tantra Evum Stree Roga*, Parul Institute of Ayurved, Parul University, Vadodara

ABSTRACT

Dysmenorrhea or painful menstruation is the most common problem faced by adolescent girls and women. Most adolescents experience primary dysmenorrhea, defined as painful menstruation of sufficient magnitude so as to incapacitate day to day activities.

We can correlate it with *yoniroga* - mainly *udavarta* or *vataj yonivyapad*. Main symptom is pain i.e., main entity is *vata*. *Acharya Charak* explained that due to *vegadharan*, *apana vayu* changes to *pratiloma gati* and the vitiated *vayu* lifts the *yonis* upward and causes obstruction to flow of *rajah* which causes unbearable pain. Here is a case report of girl 19 years with Chief complaint of painful menses suffering from primary dysmenorrhoea more than 4 cycles without any pathology. She was presented on April 2022. After her consent *Saptasaram Ghana Vati* was given with luke warm water from 1st to 5th day of menses for a cycle. As Result found was she got relief from pain during menses in her next follow up which was without medication. In this study concept of *Kashtartava* and treatment course is mentioned.

KEYWORDS: Dysmenorrhoea, *Kashtartava*, Menstruation, *Saptasaram ghana Vati*, *Udavartini Yonivyapada*

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INTRODUCTION

The word *Kashtartava* can be expressed as “*Kashtena muchyati iti Kashtartava* “that is *Kashtena* with great difficulty, so particularly the condition where *Artava* is shaded with great difficulty and pain is termed as “*Kashtartava* “

For production of *Artava*, *Vyan Vayu* and *Apana vata* work in co-ordination with each other. Contraction and Relaxation of uterus and its related organ is the function of *Vyan vayu*.

Vyan vayu has control over the muscles which bring about the actions such as contraction, relaxation after which *Artava* is expelled out by *Anulomana kriya* of *Apana vayu*.

While going through ancient text *Acharyas* have mentioned excessive use of *Katu*, *Lavana*, *Ushna*, *Tikshana ahara sevana*, *Divaswapa*, *Chinta* and *Vegadharana* as *nidanas* for *yonivyapadas* and all this responsible for *Vata* vitiation ⁽¹⁾. In present article, attempt has been made to analyze ayurvedic line of treatment in case of *Kashtartava*.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVE

1. To understand *Kashtartava* W.S.R to primary dysmenorrhoea
2. To access the effect of *Saptasaram Ghana Vati* in management of *Kashtartava*.

CASE REPORT

A girl aged 19 years who is a student, visited to *Prasuti Tantra Evum Stri Roga* OPD department of Parul Ayurved Hospital, Vadodara on April 2022 with complaints of lower abdominal pain, low backache, leg cramps during menstruation since four months.

Patient had menarche at the age of 13 years and menstrual cycle was regular. Later on cycle was followed by primary dysmenorrhoea. Pain was severe on first two days and mild on fourth day. She was getting little relief with Tab Meftal spas. As the pain was severe it was disturbing her daily

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activity. So She visited Parul Ayurved Hospital, Vadodara for advice of Dr Asokan for better treatment.

Family History
Mother - Dysmenorrhoea.

Table 1. Menstrual History

Menarche at	13 years of age
Menstrual cycle	4-5 days, Regular
Character	Dark Red color
Consistency	Clots absent
Dysmenorrhoea	Cramp like pain
Intermittent sites	Lower abdominal, low backache, legs.

Table 2. General Examinations

Built	Moderate
Nourishment	Moderate
Temperature	98.3 F
RR	20/min
Pulse Rate	74/min
Blood Pressure	110/70mmhg
Height	157cms
Weight	40kgs

Table 3. Systemic Examination

RS	AEBE clear
CVS	S1 S2 Normal
CNS	Conscious, oriented
P/A	Soft

Table 4. Gynecological Examination

Bilateral Breasts	Soft, NAD
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Table 5. Inspection of Vulva:

Pubic Hair	Moderate
Redness, Ulceration and Swelling	Absent
External urethral meatus	Normal
Evidence of pruritis	No

Table 6. Ashtavidha Pariksha:

<i>Nadi</i>	<i>Vatapradhan pitta</i>
<i>Mutra</i>	5-6 times /day
<i>Mala</i>	Once a day
<i>Jivha</i>	<i>Alipta</i>
<i>Shabda</i>	<i>Avishesha</i>
<i>Sparsha</i>	<i>Anushna Sheeta</i>
<i>Druk</i>	<i>Prakruta</i>
<i>Akruti</i>	<i>Krush</i>

Table 7. Dashvidha Pariksha

<i>Prakruti</i>	<i>Vatapradhan pitta</i>
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Vata</i>
<i>Dushya</i>	<i>Rasa, Rakta, Artava</i>
<i>Sara</i>	<i>Hina</i>
<i>Samhanana</i>	<i>Hina</i>
<i>Pramana</i>	154 cm

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<i>Satmya</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Satva</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Ahara Shakti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Vyayam Shakti</i>	<i>Hina</i>

INVESTIGATION

Table 8. USG OF ABDOMEN AND PELVIS

Liver	Normal in size
Gall bladder	Normal
Both kidneys	Normal in size and shape
Pancreas and spleen	Normal in Size
Both kidneys	Normal in Size
Uterus	Normal in Size
Endometrial echocomplex	Central and Cavity Empty
No focal mass seen	ET: 6mm
Cervix	Normal
Urine (R) and Microscopic (M)	WNL
Hb %	12.2 g/dl
B/L Ovaries	Normal

TREATMENT

LMP – 19/5/2022

Table 9. Abhyantar Yoga

Time Period	19/5/2022 to 23/5/2022
Time	TDS for 5 days
Drug	<i>Saptasaram Ghana Vati</i>
Route	Oral
Dose	500mg
<i>Anupana</i>	Luke Warm Water

Changes recommended in Lifestyle

1. Ensure sound sleep of atleast 6 to 8 hours
2. Reduce Caffeine intake
3. Eat healthy, warm and fresh foods
4. Take 4 to 5 times small meals
5. Have more leafy vegetables
6. Avoid taking high fatty food
7. Take supplement like calcium, Magnesium, Vit E, B6 and B12

Table 10. RESULTS

Date	Result
19/05/2022(Treatment Started)	lower abdominal pain, low backache, leg cramps during menstruation since four months
24/05/2022	Dysmenorrhoea was almost reduced, 80 % reduced than earlier
20/06/2022 (Without Medication)	Periods started on 15/06/2022. Dysmenorrhoea reduced. (Mild dysmenorrhea during this cycle)

Scale	BT	AT
VAS	08 (Severe Dysmenorrhoea)	02 (Mild Dysmenorrhoea)
WALIDD	09(Severe Dysmenorrhoea)	04 (Mild Dysmenorrhoea)

DISCUSSION

Saptasaram Ghana Vati ^[2]

The word *Saptasaram* means “the essence of seven” and includes *Punarnava* , *Bilwa*, *Kulattha*, *Eranda* , *Sahachara* , *Sunthi* and *Agnimantha*.

It is a great *vata* balancer and acts as an effective pain killer when it comes to gynecological problems. *Vata*, one of the *tridoshas* of the body, is also responsible for periods. So, correcting the movement of *vata dosha* is the key to have pain free menstruation.

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Punarnava (*Boerhavia diffusa*), is known to be an immunomodulator, rejuvenator and metabolism enhancer. It provides strength to pelvic organs, dysmenorrhea.

Bilwa (*Aegle marmelos*), *Kulattha* (*Dolichos Biflorus*), *Eranda* (*Ricinus communis*), *Sahachara* (*Barleria prionitis*), *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale*) and *Agnimatha* (*Premna integrifolia*) balances *tridoshas* and due to their *shoolhara* and *vatanulomana* property helps in normalizing the function of *apanavayu*. These ingredients counter acts spasmodic discovery and suppress the secretion of progesterone hormones [3]

CONCLUSION

Therapeutic effect of *Saptasaram ghana vati* showed relief in pain.

Dysmenorrhoea is common gynecological disorder and can be correlated to *Kashtartava* or *udavartini yonivyapad*. *Vata* vitiation is the main cause of menstrual disorder. Here attempt has been made to analyze the ayurvedic line of treatment and to restore the quality of life. The treatment mentioned here having *vatashamaka*, antispasmodic, anti-inflammatory properties.

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